

Autonomous Constitutional Bodies as new limits to Mexican presidentialism

— A constitutional and political debate —

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<Abstract>

This research discusses the role that Autonomous Constitutional Bodies (OCAs in Spanish) play within presidentialism in the Mexican political system. We start briefly from the evolution of the liberal state, the classic triad on the separation and division of powers and its recent evolution in Mexico until the transition to democracy in 2000. Later, it will be analyzed from a constitutional and political view, one of the main Mexican constitutional innovations that paved this path with the creation of the OCAs, which facilitated the loss of constitutional powers of the head of State and the end of imperial presidentialism. To facilitate understanding the OCAs and their legal configuration, it will be focused on the Mexican ombudsperson, which is called the National Human Rights Commission (CNDH in Spanish), which well exemplifies the limits of these institutions but also their capacity to modernize and democratize the Mexican State.

Key words: Mexico; Autonomous Constitutional Bodies; CNDH; Constitution; division and separation of powers; presidentialism

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▶ Contents ◀

1. Introduction
2. Presidentialism as a form of government and the Mexican variant
3. The Autonomous Constitutional Bodies and their legal configuration in Mexico
4. The National Human Rights Commission: its role as OCA in Mexico
5. The OCAs and the Mexican political system: a turn of the page to presidentialism and the doctrine of the separation of powers
6. Conclusions

1. Introduction

The Mexican State is configured as a presidential, federal and secular republic. Since its independence from Spain in 1821 and until the year 2000 it had few democratic experiences. However, it is interesting to analyze the Mexican political system at the end of the last century, especially because of the support that had the constitutional innovation of the Autonomous Constitutional Bodies (OCAs in Spanish). The figure of OCAs in Mexico was introduced into the Constitution in 1993 with the purpose that specialized institutions could perform functions that, due to their importance and significance, should not be subject to political decisions. They also had the purpose of accompanying the country's transition to democracy, previously characterized by single-party hyper-presidentialism. Indeed, these types of institutions independent of the other powers were an important way to democratize the Mexican State, as well as to deconcentrate political power and reduce the excessive role of the president. In this sense, it is interesting to discuss their constitutional fit, legal nature and powers that have been acquired over time.

Thus, the present investigation raises whether they suppose a fourth estate and what is their reason for being in current constitutional law, since in recent years OCAs have tended to be configured as true actors among the powers of the State. In this sense, it can highlight important functions that these institutions are acquiring like the role in

the protection of human rights, the conduct of monetary policy or the electoral processes or access to public information, among others. All of this may result in the consideration of Mexican presidentialism as a new variant of this form of government, or in the categorization of the OCAs as a new fourth estate, given its possible limitation to the federal executive power.

2. Presidentialism as a form of government and the Mexican variant

The liberal state derived from the revolutionary process of the period 1776-1830, constitutionalized the division and separation of powers. Specifically, the model advocated by Montesquieu was established,¹⁾ standing out since then as the classic triad of powers: executive, legislative and judicial. This model was put into practice for the first time in the United States Constitution of 1787 and, since then, it has been replicated by each and every liberal democracies, although with very different ways of regulating and carrying out.²⁾

Precisely, this different way of regulating the relations between the powers of the State, their constitutional powers and the election of their heads, gave rise to a question of first importance in the constitutional design: the form of State and the form of government. Regarding the first question, the form of State has passed in these two centuries between two main decisions: republic or monarchy (or rather, parliamentary monarchy). That is, a head of the State elected directly or indirectly by the people or one that, despite having an approval parliamentary procedure, basically resided in the monarchical succession, inheritance of the Old Regime and its permanence after a nineteenth century of revolutions and new constitutional approaches. However, and as discussed below, given the political irrelevance that heads of state have in parliamentary regimes, some authors such as Aragón,³⁾ points out that the real

¹⁾ Montesquieu, *El espíritu de las leyes*, Madrid: Librería General de Victoriano Suárez, 1906.

²⁾ See the cases of Costa Rica and Venezuela, where a fourth electoral power is constitutionally recognized.

³⁾ Aragón Reyes, Manuel “La democracia constitucional”, in *Constitución y Constitucionalismo Hoy. Cincuentenario del Derecho Constitucional Comparado de Manuel García Pelayo*,

debate in which current democracies are inserted in terms of the form of State is not the one related to the head of the state, but the one between liberal democracy and authoritarian regimes.⁴⁾

In relation to the form of government, a greater constitutional debate should be highlighted, as well as a profusion of political models and variants, both in their design and in their embodiment. Looking back at the birth of the liberal state after the American revolution, precisely the constitutionalists set about creating a new political model, which would have nothing to do with the then existing ones in Europe. Head of State elected by the people (although indirectly⁵⁾), a legislative power independent of the executive and legislative branch and also the result of popular suffrage, and a judicial power that diffusely controls the constitutionality of the legislation. Given the preeminence of the president of the republic or head of state over the other powers, and his symbolic character as representative of the nation, as well as his catalogs of constitutional powers, this form of government was called presidentialism.

In effect, the president of the republic is the first political and legal figure of the state. He directs it, personifies it and stands at the top of the hierarchy. It has powers in legislative matters: like veto or observation, decree and regulations. It has abundant freedom to form his government, which he directs; holds command of the armed forces and leads foreign policy; the legislature sends the annual budget bill; He cannot be removed from office except for impeachment, and his mandate is rigid, in temporal terms. Precisely, given his pre-eminence and constitutional separation over the other powers of the State, the mandate of the president of the republic is constitutionally delimited, as well as the possibility of re-election, generally established in only one.

The legislative branch, even though it is directly elected by the people, does not have an excessive capacity to influence the activity of the executive. It is not necessary for its election and permanence, and its own party conformation introduces

Fundación Manuel García-Pelayo. Caracas, pp. 93-12, 2000. Also see Aragón Reyes (2004).

⁴⁾ That is to say, the form of State should not refer to the debate between republic or monarchy, since democratic monarchies are republican in their essence and content, if not between democracy and authoritarianism.

⁵⁾ Remember the existence of an electoral college that finally elects the president of the republic.

variables that can bring both powers closer or further away. When there is the same political majority in the executive and the legislature, the unified government is established,⁶⁾ a situation that theoretically places the head of State with greater prominence, making it difficult to control and supervise legislation. Otherwise, we would be facing a divided government, which in some Latin American regimes has favored the existence of executives with a tendency to abuse the decree and to govern with their backs to the camera.⁷⁾

Precisely, this rigid and wide separation in constitutional terms between the two main political powers of the State has been habitually used as a critique in the academic sphere of presidentialism as a form of government. Given that there are hardly any mechanisms for the resolution of conflicts and the permanence of legislators, and the president is established in advance and with little capacity for alteration, there can be unsolvable clashes until the end of the mandate of each of the elected authorities. If that is added to the brief and often conflictive democratic history of much of Latin America, it can be understood that a substantial sector of the academy maintained a very pessimistic view on the stability of the regimes that barely abandoned authoritarianism after 1980.

In this sense, Mainwaring,⁸⁾ Linz and Valenzuela,⁹⁾ Nohlen,¹⁰⁾ Shugart and Carey¹¹⁾ were the first to warn about the constitutional characteristics that almost irremediably

⁶⁾ Fernandois, Arturo. "Gobierno Dividido versus Gobierno Unificado - Reflexiones sobre el Periodo Presidencial", in *Revista Chilena de Derecho* Vol. 27, no. 3, pp. 507-12, 2000.

⁷⁾ Case for example of the "delegative democracy" of Guillermo O'Donnell, who develops this concept in research such as O'Donnell, Guillermo, "Estado, Democratización y ciudadanía", en *Nueva sociedad*, no. 128, pp. 62-87, (1993). In a different sense, but one that refers to executive-legislative relations and divided government, the investigation of Ignacio García Marín for the Peruvian case can be consulted: García Marín, Ignacio. "Presidencialismo y sistema de partidos: la parlamentarización peruana (2001-2016)" in *Espiral, Estudios sobre Estado y Sociedad*, no. 74 enero-abril, 2019.

⁸⁾ Scott Mainwaring, Mainwaring, Scott, "Presidentialism in Latin America", in *Latin American Research Review*, 25(1), 157-179, 1990.

⁹⁾ Linz Juan José and Linz Arturo Valenzuela, *The breakdown of democracies*, Baltimore: Johns Hopkins University Press, 1994.

¹⁰⁾ Nohlen, Dieter, "Presidencialismo vs Parlamentarismo en América Latina". In *Revista de Estudios Políticos*, 43-54, 1991

¹¹⁾ Mathew Soberg Shugart and John M. Carey, "Presidents and Assemblies. Constitutional Design and Electoral Dynamics". Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1992.

discouraged its implementation in this region of the world with little democratic trajectory after its independence from Spain and Portugal. If we add Fujimori's self-coup in 1993 and the arrival of Hugo Chávez in 1998, everything seemed to indicate that the academic analysis was right. Fortunately, and even with some evident democratic regressions (Bolivia, Nicaragua, Venezuela), democracy was consolidated in the region and some political systems such as Uruguay, Chile and Costa Rica are among the elite of freedom at the global level.

However, and far from falling into a triumphalist vision, it is no less true that, although in its constitutional design, presidentialism seeks to consolidate the stability of the head of State and the deputies, the lack of quick mechanisms and with minorities can represent a problem in situations of notorious political confrontation. Do not forget that only impeachment is counted as a great presidential removal tool, and that its use usually requires the political majority of the legislative branch, which in practice has made its use and success relatively low.

It should be compared with parliamentarism where the political direction of the government is certainly shared between the legislature and the executive, since the latter requires a majority to approve and sustain it over time. An example of this, the head of government is the result of a parliamentary vote and not directly elected by the people; his mandate, even though it is constitutionally regulated for a period usually established in 4 years, can be terminated in advance by a motion of censure (or confidence) won by the opposition, which can be presented practically at any time during the legislature,¹²⁾ and the government, having a collegiate and usually multi-party character, does not have powers of observation or legislative veto.

Under parliamentarianism, the head of the State is located in another institution, which forces to characterize the executive as dualist, although it has few constitutional powers, being usually a moderating and cooperating role towards the different powers of the state. Likewise, although a certain constitutional primacy could be established for heads of state by democratic election over those of monarchical origin, the truth is

¹²⁾ Commonly the conditions are established in the organic laws or regulations of the legislatures. Some of the conditions tend to limit the filing of motions of no confidence to one on an annual basis or the inability to present it before 12 months of government or in the last six months of legislature.

that practice has presented both chiefdoms as true secondary actors in the political arena. That is, the form of state in a parliamentary regime does not substantially condition relations with the other powers. They do not have political autonomy and responsibility, since it is a traditional and historic role. For example, the king of Spain cannot refuse the sanction and promulgation of any bill, even one that would hypothetically eliminate the monarchy. In addition, every action it takes must be supervised and approved by the government. The 64 Constitutional article is really clear in this sense:

“The acts of the King shall be countersigned by the President of the Government and, where appropriate, by the competent Ministers. The proposal and appointment of the President of the Government, and the dissolution provided for in Article 99, shall be countersigned by the Speaker of Congress.

The persons countersigning the acts of the King shall be responsible for them.”

An important issue within parliamentarism is the existence of a multi-party system, which is increased by the generalization of governments unable to achieve a legislative majority with their own formation, that leads to coalitions and the need to negotiate and agree on a day-to-day basis. For this reason and given the importance of parliament in the fate of the executive, this form of government tends to reinforce representativeness in the design of policies with respect to presidentialism. On the contrary, it has numerous incentives for instability, although the constitutional innovation brought about by rationalized parliamentarism has reduced the preponderant role of the legislature over the executive.¹³⁾

The apparent capacity of the parliament to co-lead the government, as well as to decide its fate, has made it constitutional practice that there is no term limitation for the presidents of the government. In any case, the legislature has the aforementioned

¹³⁾ See in this regard, the double vote that the opposition must win in case of presenting a motion of censure, and which are necessarily united and continuous: desire to remove the head of government and acceptance of granting a parliamentary majority to a new president of the government. This second vote, where the opposition must agree on a successor, is certainly a great limit, given the existence in practice not of the opposition, but of several party opposition within the parliamentary arch in any democratic country.

power to present a motion of censure, which can be neutralized if the executive previously dissolved parliament by calling early elections. To avoid the abuse of the motion of censure and the volatility of governments, parliamentary constitutions tend to recognize special clauses. These special clauses are included in what is known as rationalized parliamentarism. Examples can be found in the Spanish Constitution: the constructive motion of censure (art. 113), the early calling of elections (art. 115) and the preferential processing of any bill submitted by the government (art. 88). This constitutional prerogative is very important, since it can leave the Congress Bureau in the background as there is no material or political filter for executive initiatives¹⁴).

2.1 The Mexican variant of presidentialism

Having made this brief analysis of presidentialism and its comparison with parliamentarism, it is worth dwelling on the Mexican variant. In this sense, it must be emphasized that it is a reasonably similar variant to the original model, genuinely attributed to the American one, since it was the creator of this form of government. Indeed, Mexican presidentialism, unlike other Latin American models, has not contemplated constitutional innovations such as the Peruvian one, where there is a presidency of the council of ministers (arts. 119-122); it does not contemplate the possibility of removing members of the government by the legislature, like in Peru or Colombia; nor does it establish a second round or ballot, as in most of its regional peers. However, it moves away from the US model due to the lack of a vice presidency, a position that has historically been considered to be *de facto* occupied by the government department; the presidential term is six years, thus assuming the longest of the continent's presidencies; does not recognize the possibility of reelection (art. 83); and the executive branch does have the power to present bills to the Congress (art. 71), including through an accelerated and priority process.¹⁵ On the

¹⁴) For more information is recommended Juan Luis Paniagua, "Sobre la forma de gobierno parlamentario en España: un parlamentarismo racionalizado de corte presidencial", Fundación Jiménez Abad, Estudios Parlamentarios y del Estado Autonómico, 2010.

¹⁵) Through the preferential initiative, regulated in Art. 71, section IV of the Political Constitution of the United Mexican States, however limited to only two initiatives per legislative year. The chamber where the initiative was originally presented has only 31 days

other hand, the president of the Mexican republic has tended to show a clear position of disdain or contempt for the congress regarding the annual report, a fact that is not excessively different from other presidential regimes. Similarly, the use of the veto or presidential observation (art. 72) is usually low in comparative perspective,¹⁶⁾ which could show a certain institutional respect towards the legislative chambers. However, it has corresponded more to a dominance of legislative activity by the executive even though the unified government has not taken place since 2000 except since 2018 with MORENA.

Another element that it must be taken into account is the federal character of the Mexican Republic. In effect, Mexico is constituted as a federal system, also a reflection of the influence that the American model created in the subsequent independencies that occurred on the continent. It is made up of 32 federative entities, of which Mexico City is its federal capital, although, unlike other federalisms, it can be affirmed without a doubt that the Mexican experience shows a clear domination of federal power over subnational entities, either in matters of budgets, security, health, education or commercial regulation. We are, therefore, facing a federalism of low depth due to the centralization of political and economic activity in its capital and the federal powers.

Table 1. The presidentialism of the United States and Mexico.

	Presidentialism (American model)	Mexican presidentialism
Direct and independent election of legislators	Yes	Yes
Direct and independent election of the president	No	Yes
Fixed term president	Yes	Yes
Legislators fixed term	Yes	Yes
President can be removed impeachment	Yes	Yes
Congress can be dissolved by president	No	No
Existence of prime minister	No	No
President has legislative initiative	No	Yes

to discuss it and vote on it in the plenary session.

¹⁶⁾ Pérez Liñán, Aníbal y Rodríguez Raga, Juan Carlos. “Veto players in presidential regimes: institutional variables and policy change”, in *Revista de Ciencia Política*, vol. 29, no. 3, pp. 693-720, 2009.

	Presidentialism (American model)	Mexican presidentialism
Legislative is bicameral	Yes	Yes
Presidential reelection	Yes, maximum 2 terms	No
Existence Vice President	Yes one	No
Congress president	Vice President of the Republic	Deputy, elected by the chamber

Source: own elaboration based on the Constitution of the United States of Mexico.

2.2 The transition to democracy in Mexico: a political, economic and social context that constitutionally reconfigured the republic.

To analyze the Mexican presidential system its political practice must be taken into consideration, especially when we are talking about a regime that only entered the democratic era in 2000, after the presidential victory of Vicente Fox, of the National Action Party (PAN in Spanish). Indeed, between 1917, the date on which the current constitution came into force, and the year 2000, this North American country suffered from a party-based authoritarian regime, dominated in a hegemonic way by the Institutional Revolutionary Party (PRI in Spanish).¹⁷⁾ During this long time, the country was characterized by the practice of hyper-presidentialism, given the non-existent separation between the powers of the State and the submission of the legislature and the judiciary to the Head of State. The president of the republic himself was elected by the party leadership in a process that was neither democratic nor transparent¹⁸⁾ and the electoral processes in the country were a fiction without partisan competition.¹⁹⁾ The governors of the states were often selected by the president of the republic and a collusion between the country's political and economic elites was the norm throughout the PRI regime.²⁰⁾ The two great pillars of the authoritarian system of the last century

¹⁷⁾ National Revolutionary Party (1929-1939); Party of the Mexican Revolution (1939-1946) and finally the Institutionalized Revolutionary Party (since 1946).

¹⁸⁾ Pablo González Casanova, “*La democracia en México*”, Ciudad de México: Ediciones Era, 1975.

¹⁹⁾ Barrón, Luis, “La transición a la democracia en México con perspectiva histórica”, in *Política y Gobierno*, XIII(1), 175-190, 2006.

²⁰⁾ Muñoz Petracá, “Transición a la democracia en México”, in *Revista Mexicana de Ciencias*

were the hegemonic party and hyper-presidentialism.²¹⁾

The way to end with this authoritarian and personalistic combination was the growing loss of political power and constitutional faculties (including meta-constitutional) of the executive. Example of that, the executive lost control of the electoral process and there were increasingly public subsidies to create new political parties. The international environment also helped the transition to democracy, since the rivalry between the US and the USSR was ending and many Latin American countries was also taking a democratizing process, unstoppable in the long term. In this sense, it is necessary to highlight the electoral reforms of 1977, 1986, 1991, 1994 and 1996 as they reduced the predominance of the PRI in the legislature, encouraged party competition, increased the representativeness of the Congress of the Union and, finally, allowed the holding credible and reliable elections. Result of this in 1997 the president Ernesto Zedillo was placed in a divided government,²²⁾ a fact that never happened since 1917.

Therefore, it has to be highlighted a path through which the country traveled to finally achieve democracy, that is undoubtedly the loss of powers in the presidential figure,²³⁾ since the professionalization and impartiality of the institutions in charge was the one that ultimately allowed the opposition for the first time to take power in a legitimate and peaceful manner and to strengthen the legislative power as a truly separate and autonomous power from the executive, as well as a growing specialization in decision-making in economic matters, protection of human rights or electoral matters, among many others. That is, the creation of specialized agencies with an eminently technical nature and with some autonomy over the executive, as discussed in the following sections.

An example of this growing electoral democracy and loss of powers by the

Políticas y Sociales, 39 (157), pp. 9-23, 1994.

21) Cossio Villegas, Daniel, “*El sistema político mexicano*”. Ciudad de México: Cuadernos de Joaquín Mortiz, 1972.

22) Escamilla Cadena, Arturo, “Presidencialismo transición a la democracia en México. En M. G. Enrique Cuna, *México entre siglos. contexto, balance y agenda*, Ciudad de México: UAM-PRD, pp. 167-181, 2016.

23) Méndez de Hoyos, I, Transición y consolidación democrática en México ¿es posible una regresión?, in *Revista de la Facultad de Derecho de México*, 57(247), pp. 63-70, 2007.

executive happened in 1996, when a higher court specialized in electoral matters was created, it was called the Electoral Tribunal of the Federal Judicial Power, (TEPJF in Spanish). It came previously accompanied by the creation in 1990 of the Federal Electoral Institute (IFE in Spanish and currently INE in Spanish) for the purpose of holding the electoral processes and establishing the regulatory framework for it.²⁴⁾ Until then, the elections were monitored and held by the executive itself, which explains well the conflict of interest and the lack of institutional guarantees that characterized the electoral process in Mexico for decades. Similarly, it should be noted that the judiciary had until then maintained a certain but hard separation from the executive, managing not to be subject in the same way as Congress, but without an activist role. Based on various historical investigations, apparently the judiciary intervened as a brake against evident abuses or authoritarian acts, usually through the application of appeal (*amparo* in Mexican law) , although not in a generalized way.

This entire process of reform, mainly developed in the last two decades of the last century, was accompanied by an opening economic context, that is the entry into the GATT in 1985, the autonomous reconfiguration of the Bank of Mexico in 1993, and the entry into force in 1994 of the free trade agreement with the United States and Canada (NAFTA in English). No less remarkable is the fact that the transition to democracy in Mexico had a clear progressive feature and was controlled from political power. Therefore, it is not strange the great debate that exists around the start and end date of the democratic transition, as well as the apparent lack of a clear break with the authoritarian past.²⁵⁾

In conclusion, it can be highlighted that during the democratic transition in Mexico three main objectives were sought: the brake of dominant political power, especially the executive power; the creation of mechanisms and processes in electoral matters that were reliable, safe and with real capacity for the opposition to be able to govern; and a progressive detachment of powers and tasks of the executive in very diverse areas,

²⁴⁾ Muñoz Petracca, *op. cit.*, pp. 9-23, 1994.

²⁵⁾ Generally, the end of the transition is established in the year 2000, although 1997 is also a reference date given the loss of the legislative majority of the PRI. On the other hand, it is more difficult to locate its beginning, with the fraud of the 1988 elections being the year with the greatest consensus as the beginning of the process.

which were transferred to specialized and autonomous bodies with constitutional rank, called OCAs, a topic that is discussed in the following section.

3. The Autonomous Constitutional Bodies and their legal configuration in Mexico

As it has just been commented, in the 1990s and under the presidency of the PRI, technical and specialized institutions called Autonomous Constitutional Organs (OCAs in Spanish) were introduced to carry out new public functions of regulation, surveillance and control, historically performed by the executive power.²⁶⁾ There are at least two doctrinal positions from which an attempt has been made to explain the appearance and growing evolution of these institutions in Mexico: on the one hand, some authors²⁷⁾ share the opinion that the main reason that has decisively favored the appearance of these organizations is, first, the loss of the legitimacy of democratic institutions and the complexity in public administration and, second, the demand for citizen spaces of more plural action vis-à-vis by the public power, with the aim of nonpartisan, decorporate and democratize the governing bodies of the State, through bodies outside the political forces and endowed with recognized prestige and

²⁶⁾ Fabián Ruíz, José. “Los órganos constitucionales autónomos en México”, in *Cuestiones Constitucionales Revista Mexicana de Derecho Constitucional*, núm. 37, julio-diciembre, México, UNAM-IIIJ, p. 90, 2017.

²⁷⁾ Some authors who have agreed on this thesis are Carbonell, Miguel, *Elementos de derecho constitucional*, México, Fontamara, p. 55 *et seq.*, 2006; Cárdenas Gracia, Jaime, “Justificación de los órganos constitucionales autónomos”, en *Derecho y Cultura*, no. 2, México, UNAM-IIIJ, pp. 17 and 18, (2001); Pedroza de la Llave, Susana Thalía, “Los órganos constitucionales autónomos en México”, en Serna de la Garza, José María y Caballero Juárez, José Antonio, (eds.), *Estado de Derecho y transición jurídica*, México, IJJ-UNAM, pp. 179 and 180, (2002); Rodríguez Doníz, Álvaro, “Prospección política de los OPA: la rendición de cuentas y el uso de las TIC como detonadores de la recuperación institucional (credibilidad-confianza) en el contexto de la política informal” en *Memorias del Octavo Congreso Nacional de Organismos Públicos Autónomos. La participación ciudadana en el fortalecimiento de los OPA*, México, CDHDF, p. 212, (2013); Córdova, Vianello, Lorenzo, “Estado actual y futuro de los órganos autónomos”, en *Memorias del Tercer Congreso Nacional de Organismos Públicos Autónomos. Autonomía, Reforma Legislativa y Gasto Público*, México, CDFDF, p. 15, 2008.

experience in the matter. Indeed, for these authors, the OCAs are “those bodies immediate and fundamental established in the Constitution and that are not clearly ascribed to any of the traditional powers of the State. They are bodies of constitutional and political balance whose criteria for action are to preserve the constitutional organization and functioning”.²⁸⁾ Thereby, The explanation or justification for the emergence of OCAs may be both for reasons of administrative division of labor in search of greater effectiveness and efficiency, accompanied by the need or priority assigned to a redistribution of state power in search of new balances between the political forces that lead the political and administrative decision.²⁹⁾

On the other hand, a minority sector³⁰⁾ defends that its creation has meant a weakening of the government without necessarily strengthening the State, since they have generated new administrative problems, particularly related to inter-institutional coordination, as well as a harmful transformation to the classic theory of the division of powers. On these arguments, however, certain limits have been recognized in terms of the lack of an in-depth empirical analysis that helps to adequately demonstrate the alleged distortion suffered by the State by the supposed fashion³¹⁾ of these organisms.

Now, in Mexico there is no constitutional precept that regulates and recognizes a definition or existence of such bodies, however, there are some authors who have tried to explain this figure. For Jaime Cárdenas “there are those immediate and fundamental

²⁸⁾ Estrada Michel, Rafael (comp.) *La división del poder público. Temas constitucionales*, Porrúa, México, p. 158, 2007.

²⁹⁾ Castellanos Hernández, Eduardo de Jesús, “*Los órganos constitucionales autónomos, antes y después del pacto por México*”, in Carbonell Sánchez, Miguel y Cruz Barney, Óscar (coords.), *Historia y Constitución. Homenaje a José Luis Soberanes Fernández*, tomo II, México, UNAM-III, p. 94, 2015.

³⁰⁾ In this position there are authors for whom “the multiplication of autonomous islands may constitute an obstacle to the effective functioning of the Mexican State, especially in those bodies whose mission does not require autonomy, or, when autonomy can just politicize its operation”. *Cfr.* Ugalde, Luis Carlos, “En la marea de la baja calidad del Estado”, en *Nexos*, mayo, 2014, available in <https://www.nexos.com.mx/?p=20787>. As well as Dussauge Laguna, Mauricio, “Mitos y realidades de los órganos constitucionales autónomos mexicanos”, en *Revista de Administración Pública*, núm. 138, México, UNAM-III, September-December, pp. 233 *et seq.*, 2015.

³¹⁾ Luis Carlos Ugalde has referred that “it has become a cliché to demand autonomy every time a performance problem is detected or simply because of fashion”, *cfr.* Ugalde, Luis Carlos, “En la marea de la baja calidad del Estado”, *op. cit.*

established in the Constitution and that are not clearly ascribed to any of the traditional powers of the state”.³²⁾ Ileana Moreno describes the OCAs as “atypical public law legal entities, which do not depend on any of the three traditional branches”.³³⁾ García Pelayo, for his part, has indicated some distinction criteria of these bodies which are: immediacy, for appearing in the Constitution itself; essentiality, due to its democratic necessity; political leadership, for decisively guiding the state decision-making process; rank parity, for being supreme in his sphere of competence and independent in his functions; organic, functional and sometimes budgetary autonomy.³⁴⁾

Specifically, the Supreme Court of Justice has established certain elements inherent to their legal nature that show that it is an OCA, they are a) to be established and configured directly in the Constitution; b) to maintain coordination relationships with the other bodies of the State; c) to have functional and financial autonomy and independence and d) to attend to conjunctural functions of the State that need to be effectively attended to for the benefit of society.³⁵⁾ It is, in summary, a system through which the Mexican federal Constitution places in an equal place³⁶⁾ these independent bodies and those which represent the traditional powers (executive, legislative and judicial), in order to carry out specific state functions in search of greater specialization, agility and transparency in their performance.³⁷⁾

Thus, the Mexican Constitution currently recognizes nine OCAs, namely, the Bank

³²⁾ Cárdenas Gracia, Jaime, *Una Constitución para la democracia. Propuestas para un nuevo orden constitucional*, 2a. ed., México, UNAM-IIIJ, p. 244, 2012.

³³⁾ Moreno Ramírez, Ileana, *Los órganos constitucionales autónomos en el ordenamiento jurídico mexicano*, México, Porrúa, p. XIV, 2005.

³⁴⁾ García Pelayo, Manuel, “El ‘status’ del Tribunal Constitucional”, in *Revista Española de Derecho Constitucional*, Madrid, Centro de Estudios Constitucionales, núm. 1, p. 12, 1981.

³⁵⁾ The judgment handed down by the Plenary of the Supreme Court of Justice of the Nation on May 22, 2006, in the constitutional controversy 32/2005, was published in the Judicial Weekly of the Federation and its Gazette, Novena Época, t. XXIV, October 2006.

³⁶⁾ The SCJN indicated with respect to these organizations that “they are on a par with the traditional organs.” See the jurisprudence AUTONOMOUS CONSTITUTIONAL BODIES. DISTINCTIVE NOTES AND CHARACTERISTICS, Judicial Weekly of the Federation and its Gazette, t. XXV, May 2007, p. 1647, registration 172,456.

³⁷⁾ Fabián Ruíz, José, “Los órganos constitucionales autónomos en México”, *op. cit.*, p. 93, 2017.

of Mexico (BANXICO in Spanish), in charge of ensuring the stability of the purchasing power of the national currency, as well as providing the healthy development of the financial system and promoting the proper functioning of payment systems;³⁸⁾ the Federal Economic Competition Commission (COFECE in Spanish), to promote, protect and guarantee free competition and economic competition, prevent, investigate and combat monopolies and monopolistic practices;³⁹⁾ the National Council for the Evaluation of Social Development Policy (CONEVAL in Spanish), in order to guarantee the exercise, ensuring the access of the entire population to social development;⁴⁰⁾ the Office of the Attorney General of the Republic (FGR in Spanish), with the purpose of investigating federal crimes and seeking justice and adequate reparation for the victims;⁴¹⁾ the Federal Telecommunications Institute (IFT in Spanish), to regulate matters related to the radioelectric spectrum, public telecommunications networks, satellite communication and, in general, public telecommunications and broadcasting services;⁴²⁾ the National Institute of Statistics and Geography (INEGI in Spanish), to provide society and the State with quality, pertinent, truthful and timely information, in order to contribute to national development;⁴³⁾ the National Institute of Transparency, Access to Information and Protection of Personal Data (INAI in Spanish), in order to protect the rights of access to public information held by any authority that receives and exercises public resources⁴⁴⁾ and the data protection of all persons in possession of the obligated subjects;⁴⁵⁾ the National Electoral Institute (INE

38) Article 28, sixth and seventh paragraphs of the Federal Constitution and article 2 of the Bank of Mexico Law.

39) Article 28 of the Federal Constitution and Article 2 of the Federal Law on Economic Competition.

40) Article 26, section C of the Federal Constitution and article 1, section I of the General Law of Social Development.

41) Article 102 of the Federal Constitution and Articles 1 and 2 of the Organic Law of the Attorney General's Office.

42) Article 28 of the Federal Constitution and Article 1 of the Federal Telecommunications and Broadcasting Law.

43) Article 26, section B of the Federal Constitution and article 3 of the Law of the National System of Statistical and Geographical Information.

44) Article 6, section VIII of the Federal Constitution and article 1, second paragraph of the General Law of Transparency and Access to Public Information.

45) Article 1, fourth paragraph of the General Law on Protection of Personal Data Held by

in Spanish), for the organization and implementation of federal and local electoral processes;⁴⁶⁾ and the National Human Rights Commission (CNDH in Spanish), whose main function is the protection and promotion of human rights.⁴⁷⁾

Regarding the legal configuration of these bodies, there is no homogeneity in their regulation, structure or composition, however, in all of them, it stands out their functional and financial autonomy, without which their nature and effectiveness would be seriously affected. Indeed, functional autonomy requires that they have their own competencies without being subject to the intervention of other powers, as well as appoint their own personnel based on specific criteria.⁴⁸⁾ In the case of financial autonomy, it is important to project their economic needs from their plan of activities and exercise the resources in accordance with their own efforts,⁴⁹⁾ although this does not mean that they are not subject to the control, surveillance and supervision that the supreme authorities of the State can exercise.⁵⁰⁾ This is, beyond the responsibility linked to serious administrative faults or acts of corruption and property of the State applicable to all public servants (Fourth Title of the Federal Constitution).

Specifically, there are various elements that must be taken into account in an OCAS control system, in relation to the body in question. Thus, for example, in some cases reports of activities must be submitted to the legislative and executive branches and have appearances at the request of the legislative branch (in the case of COFECE, IFT and CNDH); in others, it must have the figure of an internal comptroller for the control of income and expenses (case of IFT, COFECE and INE).

Another common note in their design of these bodies is that they constitute an efficient counterweight because they promote non-partisan citizen participation in fundamental decision-making.⁵¹⁾ Therefore, among the requirements of its members is

Obliged Subjects.

46) Article 41, section V of the Federal Constitution and article 1.1. of the General Law of Electoral Institutions and Procedures.

47) Article 102, section B, of the Federal Constitution and article 2 of the Law on the National Human Rights Commission.

48) Fabián Ruíz, José, “Los órganos constitucionales autónomos en México”, *op. cit.*, p. 103, 2017.

49) *Ibidem*, pp. 112 and 113.

50) Matheus, María Milagros, “Relaciones de los institutos autónomos con la administración central”, en *Cuestiones Políticas*, no. 14, Venezuela, pp. 123 *et seq.*, 1995.

to have experience in the field they are going to occupy, to be technical officials of recognized prestige in academic and professional fields and not to belong to any political party.

However, recently, and beyond their inherent powers to each body, some of them have been recognized with the power to defend both their own constitutionally conferred powers, as well as to raise the possible contradiction between general norms and the federal Constitution. In other words, they have been endowed with active legitimacy before the Supreme Court of Justice of the Nation (SCJN in Spanish), to file constitutional controversies, in the first case, and unconstitutionality actions, in the second. This situation of interaction between the powers of the State and the autonomous constitutional bodies could be explained by the relevance that they have acquired over time.⁵²⁾ When referring to the constitutional controversies that article 105, section I of the Constitution attributes to resolve to the SCJN, on the constitutionality of general norms, acts and omissions, it can be observed that, according to subsection k) they are considered conflicts that arise between two autonomous constitutional bodies of a federative entity, and between one of these and the executive power or the legislative power of that federative entity, as well as l) two federal autonomous constitutional bodies, and between one of these and the union executive branch or union congress. In this way, “this constitutional guarantee is intended to preserve the system of distribution of powers between the different levels of government and between the different powers”.⁵³⁾

A similar situation occurs in the case of unconstitutionality actions contemplated by article 105, section II, subsections g), h) and i) of the Federal Constitution, with the

⁵¹⁾ Caballero Ochoa, José Luis, “Los órganos constitucionales autónomos: más allá de la división de poderes”, en *Jurídica, Anuario del Departamento de Derecho de la Universidad Iberoamericana*, no. 30, México, Universidad Iberoamericana, 2000, p. 156, 2000.

⁵²⁾ José Luis Caballero has pointed out that “it seems at times that the autonomous constitutional bodies would have a special prevalence even above the powers, in addition to the fact that some, such as the *ombudsman*, have acquired an importance of the highest order”, *cf.*, *Idem*.

⁵³⁾ Isolated thesis 2a. LXXXVIII / 98, “CONSTITUTIONAL DISPUTES. A DECENTRALIZED STATE PUBLIC ORGANISM LACKS ACTIVE LEGITIMATION IN THE CASE”, *Judicial Weekly of the Federation and its Gazette*, Ninth Epoch, t. VII, June 1998, p. 421, registration: 903,862.

exception that not all OCAs are provided for the filing of the appeal if a series of circumstances concur. This more restrictive doctrine has been recognized only by the CNDH, the INAI and the FGR, although with differences between them. By way of example, the CNDH has the right to appeal against laws of a federal nature or of the federative entities, as well as international treaties signed by the federal executive and approved by the Senate of the Republic, that violate the human rights established in the Mexican Constitution and in the international treaties to which Mexico is a party. For its part, the INAI, even with the same power to promote unconstitutional actions, is only allowed to do so with respect to those laws that violate the right of access to public information and the protection of personal data. Finally, the FGR will be able to do it like the two previous organisms exclusively with respect to federal laws and those of the federative entities in criminal matters and criminal procedure, as well as those related to the scope of its functions.

4. The National Human Rights Commission: its role as OCA in Mexico

We now explain one of the perhaps most representative examples in which an authentic evolution of an OCA in Mexico can be seen, not only in terms of its internal powers with other State institutions, but also with respect to its interaction with supranational bodies such as the inter-American system. To begin with, it should be remembered that this institution was initially created as a decentralized body of the Ministry of Home Affairs (1990). Later it was incorporated into the federal Constitution as a decentralized body (1992), and years later (1999),⁵⁴ it acquired its own legal personality and autonomy through the figure of OCA. The differences are relevant because while, as a deconcentrated and decentralized body, the appointment of its head was directly in charge of the executive power, that faculty passes to the

⁵⁴) José Fabián Ruíz has called “first generation pioneer bodies” those that emerged from 1993 in the Mexican Constitution, among which are, in addition to the CNDH, the Bank of Mexico whose autonomy acquired it since 1980 and the National Electoral Institute incorporated as OCA in 1996. *Cf.*, Fabián Ruíz, José, “Los órganos constitucionales autónomos en México”, *op. cit.*, p. 86, 2017.

chamber of senators when it acquires its autonomy. Thus, article 102, section B of the constitutional text recognized the CNDH as an OCA in the following terms:

“The Congress of the Union and the legislatures of the federative entities, within the scope of their respective competences, will establish *human rights protection bodies that protect the Mexican legal order*, which will hear complaints against acts or omissions of a nature. administrative authority from any public authority or servant, with the exception of the Judicial Power of the Federation, who violate these rights [···].

The body established by the Congress of the Union shall *be called the National Human Rights Commission; it will have management and budgetary autonomy, legal personality and its own assets.*” (emphasis added).

As can be seen from the aforementioned, the CNDH, as an OCA, was in charge of the main objective of protecting human rights in Mexico, an issue that served to be recognized that same year as a National Human Rights Institution (INDH in Spanish) by United Nations, in terms of the Paris Principles. Since then, this body has a president who lasts for five years and an advisory council made up of ten people elected by the same mechanism for electing the president, that is, by two-thirds of the Senate. This is the only way to guarantee that the CNDH maintains its autonomy and is a benchmark in the non-jurisdictional protection of human rights.

In fact, its work is important not only in terms of the protection and repair of rights, but also in its activity of promotion, study and dissemination of human rights, both nationally and internationally (articles 2 and 6, section IX of the CNDH Law). At the national level, this allows it to suggest reforms on certain public policies on human rights, as it has done on recent occasions in matters of forced disappearances and the phenomenon of Internal Forced Displacement (DFI in Spanish), in which, through testimonies collected by CNDH staff, as well as the analysis of current legislation, the CNDH has highlighted the absence of a diagnosis on the matter, as well as official statistics that allow measuring the consequences of such phenomena.⁵⁵⁾

⁵⁵⁾ See various CNDH documents on Forced Internal Displacement, including the Special Report on DFI, available at [http://informe.cndh.org.mx/menu.aspx?id=15008#:~:text=El % 2011% 20de% 20mayo% 20de, Internal% 20 \(DFI\)% 20en% 20M% C3% A9xico. & Text = Likewis](http://informe.cndh.org.mx/menu.aspx?id=15008#:~:text=El%2011%20de%20mayo%20de,Internal%20(DFI)%20en%20M%C3%A9xico.&Text=Likewis)

Consequently, it has proposed the elaboration of a general diagnosis that allows taking actions and preventing crimes. In this sense, thanks in part to his management, the Federal Congress has reviewed and proposed various initiatives with the aim of regulating such conduct and repairing the victims. Internationally, the CNDH has also promoted various agreements to promote a culture of human rights. For example, it can be mentioned the promotion of a Rights Book for Mexican migrants who are illegally in the United States, allowing them to have a guide regarding their rights that will assist them if they are detained, as well as contact telephone numbers for the embassy, consulate and civil organizations that can help you during the detention procedure. This booklet has been distributed on the internet through social networks and also physically, thanks to the collaboration of other institutions such as the headquarters of the National Autonomous University of Mexico (UNAM in Spanish) in that country. Therefore, through the preventive work of the CNDH, it seeks to avoid future human rights violations, this function being fundamental both for government authorities and for people in general, since the purpose is to educate in human rights through learning, knowledge and the culture of legality and to be able to achieve a culture of human rights with adherence to the respect of universal standards. Another purpose is that fewer cases end up in the ordinary courts and in the CNDH itself and that everyone knows their rights and obligations in the area of human rights.

Resuming its restorative function, the CNDH is an institution whose defense of human rights control is carried out through the recommendation, trust, and suggestive and prestigious force of the individual in whom the position comes to personify.⁵⁶⁾ The recommendations issued, therefore, are not binding, however, in the event of their rejection by the authorities, the Chamber of Senators may call public servants to explain the reason for their refusal. This type of political control that the CNDH has to comply with its recommendations, although it has not been used in its history, as it

e% 2C% 20collects% 20testimonies% 20de% 20displacements, states% 20de% 20la% 20Rep% C3% BAblica% 20Mexicana; as well as the General Proposal to request the present initiative of a general law on DFI, available at https://www.cndh.org.mx/sites/all/doc/Otros_Documentos/Doc_2018_063.pdf.

⁵⁶⁾ PÉrgola, Antonio La, “Ombudsman y defensor del pueblo: apuntes para una investigación comparada”, en *Revista de Estudios Políticos*, Madrid, no. 7, p. 77, (1977).

is not a court, has the virtue of being able to demand from the authorities a minimal, well-founded response.

Below you can see the number of recommendations that the CNDH has issued from its creation in 1990 to the last period of its head in 2019. Being the second period (1993-1996) in which the greatest number of recommendations were issued; as well as the rights to life, health and personal integrity and security the most violated.

Table 2. Total recommendations issued by the CNDH.

Periods	Number of years in each period	Total recommendations issued	Rights most violated
1) from June 6, 1990 to January 13, 1993	4	435	Personal integrity and safety
2) from January 14, 1993 to November 26, 1996	4	702	Personal integrity and safety
3) from January 8, 1997 to November 13, 1999	3	344	Personal integrity and safety, right to health
4) from November 16, 1999 to November 15, 2009	11	567	Personal integrity and security, right to health, right to life
5) from November 16, 2009 to November 15, 2014	6	417	Right to life, right to health, right to personal integrity and security
6) from November 16, 2014 to November 15, 2019	6	401	Right to life, right to health, right to personal integrity and security

Source: Own elaboration based on information obtained from the CNDH website.

Finally, it should be mentioned the powers that the CNDH has been acquiring over time, especially due to its role as OCA. Such is the case of constitutional controversies and constitutional actions, to which it has resorted on more than one occasion. As an example, the constitutional controversy 45/2019 is exposed, in which the CNDH considered detrimental to its constitutional competence, specifically its budgetary and management autonomy, the Decree of Budget of Expenditures of the Federation for the Fiscal Year 2019, issued by the Chamber of Deputies of the

Congress of the Union and the President of the Republic. The foregoing, since when the act was issued, the budget project prepared by the National Commission was rejected, and by reducing it even more, it was prevented from applying article 127 of the Constitution to set the remuneration of its public servants in the exercise of their autonomy and independence, directly and immediately affecting the sphere of attributions established for the CNDH as an autonomous constitutional body. Thus, as the CNDH pointed out, the decrease in the budget prepared for the fiscal year 2019 affected its constitutional jurisdiction, which resulted in a direct violation of its budgetary autonomy.⁵⁷⁾ In addition, it was argued that the Federation's Expenditure Budget, by providing that the remuneration of public servants in command and of the highest representation of the CNDH must be lower than that established for the office of President of the Republic, violates the same article 127, section III of the Mexican Constitution since, in accordance with that provision, public servants can receive remuneration as a consequence of their performance of various public jobs, the product of the general conditions of their work, derived from a qualified technical work or by specialization of its function, thus limiting, in the same way, the budgetary autonomy of the CNDH.⁵⁸⁾

Regarding the actions of unconstitutionality promoted by the CNDH, the 4/2019 can be cited against the legislative body of Tamaulipas and the governor of the same Federative Entity. In particular, regarding Article 17 Ter, seventh paragraph, section I of the Political Constitution of Tamaulipas, which stated that:

“The right to identity established in section VII of article 17 of this Constitution will be guaranteed by means of a state identity card. The state identity card is a personal and non-transferable identification, which will be issued by the Institute established for it in this Constitution. All citizens of the State will have the right to have the identity card and its obtaining will be mandatory for residents over fourteen years of age and those living in the State who remain in the State for a period greater than six months. The ID will be governed by the

⁵⁷⁾ Constitutional Controversy 45/2019, pp. 14 and following, available at https://www.cndh.org.mx/sites/default/files/documentos/2019-06/Con_Const_2019_45.pdf.

⁵⁸⁾ Constitutional Controversy 45/2019, pp. 16 and following, available at https://www.cndh.org.mx/sites/default/files/documentos/2019-06/Con_Const_2019_45.pdf

principles of legality, confidentiality and certainty. The body that guarantees this right will be the State Institute for Identity Protection. It will be a body with technical, budgetary and management autonomy, as well as with its own legal personality and assets. The Institute will be the authority in the matter, independent and autonomous in its decisions.

It will be made up of a Presiding Commissioner and two Commissioners. The Law of the matter will determine the form of its integration and functions. The Commissioners must meet the following requirements: I.- Be a Mexican citizen *by birth* and be in full enjoyment of their civil and political rights; (···)” (emphasis added).

From the above transcript, it follows that one of the requirements to join the State Institute for Identity Protection is to be a Mexican citizen by birth. Hence, the expression *by birth* was considered by the CNDH to violate various constitutional and conventional precepts, among them articles 1, 5, 32 and 35, section VI, of the federal Constitution; Articles 1 and 24 of the American Convention on Human Rights (CADH in Spanish); Articles 2.1, 25, subsection c), and 26 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights; Articles 2.2 and 6 of the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights and Article 2 of Convention 111 of the International Labor Organization, Relating to Discrimination in the Matters of Employment and Occupation. As well as violated human rights to equality, non-discrimination, work and the right to be appointed for any job or public service commission.

Among its arguments and citing both the federal constitutional text and the CADH, the jurisprudence of the Inter-American Court of Human Rights (Inter-American Court) and various criteria of the SCJN, the CNDH stated that the category *by birth* referred to a suspicious category, for what its incorporation into the constitutional text of a Federal Entity is associated with cultural devaluation, social disadvantage and political marginalization,⁵⁹⁾ sufficient reasons to go against the rights to equality and non-discrimination, protected by those same legal systems. Regarding the right to work, the CNDH specified that no person can be prevented from engaging in a lawful

⁵⁹⁾ Action of Unconstitutionality 4/2019, p. 9, available at https://www.cndh.org.mx/sites/default/files/documentos/2019-02/Acc_Inc_2019_4.pdf

activity that is of their choice and, in this sense, Mexican citizens have the right to be appointed to hold public office. Next, the CNDH stated that, although the federal Constitution in its article 32 establishes the possibility of determining the positions and functions in which it may be required to be Mexican by birth, such power does not correspond to the local legislatures, but rather It is exclusive to the federal legislator, since the congresses of the federative entities are not constitutionally empowered to establish this requirement.⁶⁰⁾

The preceding paragraphs seem to serve as sufficient proof of the evident presence of the CNDH as an autonomous institution of the State and its potential influence on various relevant issues. Budgetary and functional autonomy are the basis for determining their continued defense of their own affairs, as well as for guaranteeing adequate protection of human rights.

Another interesting date in the evolution that the configuration of the CNDH has had since its creation in 1990 and as OCA in 1999, was 2011 with the reform of human rights at the federal level. From that moment on, the function of investigating serious human rights violations from the SCJN was transferred to the CNDH, a situation that has led it to issue recommendations for serious violations ever since.⁶¹⁾ On the other hand, and also as a consequence of the 2011 reform, a specific duty was introduced for all authorities within the scope of their competences (including the CNDH), to follow the jurisprudence derived from the Inter-American Court, with which, the CNDH has had an increasing collaboration with the inter-American system. As an example, it can be cited the figure of *amicus curiae* that the CNDH has presented before the Inter-American Court in 2005 and 2017. As well as the role it has played as an adjunct in the compliance of the inter-American judgments by the Mexican State in the years 2009, 2010, 2011 and 2013.

This duty to follow the jurisprudence of the Inter-American Court by the CNDH, in turn, has led to a greater argumentative quality in the recommendations of the CNDH as concepts and legal figures that have been developed in the inter-American

⁶⁰⁾ Action of Unconstitutionality 4/2019, p. 7 and following, available at https://www.cndh.org.mx/sites/default/files/documentos/2019-02/Acc_Inc_2019_4.pdf

⁶¹⁾ The recommendations for serious violations issued by the CNDH can be seen in Table 1 in the fifth and sixth periods.

headquarters have been incorporated, such as the right to the truth, reproductive rights, the rights of people deprived of liberty, among others.

Finally, we find an interesting result of these constitutional warranties. In first order, the CNDH has the faculty to stop the executive and legislative decisions that may impact their autonomy and functioning. It is really important in a country with little democratic legacy, mainly because of the dominion of an authoritarian elite. Secondly, but linked to this previous point, the relation between the executive and the OCAS can be a new way to measure and analyze the quality of Mexican democracy. In this sense, the aim of the presidents and main parties of the chamber can be tested. The presidential election of 2006, where the runner-up López Obrador did not recognize the results, is a good imagen. Also, the resistance of the former president Peña Nieto (2012-2018) to accept the tragedy and serious violation of human rights in Ayotzinapa, in 2014⁶²). Currently, the Head of state, López Obrador (2018-2024) is denying the legitimacy of the OCAS to organize electoral processes, inform about public expenditures or research some alleged human rights violations in the Mexican - Guatemalan border. For these reasons, we can see a political path: the OCAS can be an unpleasant limit to the authoritarian presidents.

5. The OCAs and the Mexican political system: a turn of the page to presidentialism and the doctrine of the separation of powers

As previously mentioned, the contemporary liberal system rests its organic base on the doctrine of the division and separation of the powers of the State. This conception occurs regardless of the form of government, although the different configuration that presidentialism, parliamentarism and hybrid regimes (usually called semi-presidential) print must be recognized. However, since its implementation from the revolutionary process of the period 1780-1830 to the present day, the constitutional powers of the

⁶²) In 2014, in the town of Ayotzinapa, 43 students disappeared apparently in a joint crime between the drugs cartel and the municipal and local authorities. The case is yet under investigation for the national and Inter American authorities.

powers of the State, as well as their checks and balances and the role of each of them, has varied from one to another. Of course, it should be mentioned the importance of political majorities to understand the functioning of any political system.

All this, however, it must come hand in hand with the recognition that the relations between the powers of the State have always been conflictive, cooperative, or denied each other. That is to say, there is no absolute or healthy true separation of powers, if not that the constitutional design itself and the distribution of constitutional powers of each one of them, foresees very different situations between them, although one of the principles of the constitutional state is the to limit and distribute political power. In fact, the separation of powers “does not only consist in the division of labor: it also implies that the different governmental bodies are independent of each other”,⁶³⁾ as Loewenstein highlights.⁶⁴⁾ The ultimate objective of the separation of powers is to ensure freedom, seeking to avoid the abuse of power or its excessive concentration.

On the other hand, it should be noted that the creation of OCAS is a true *sui generis* innovation in constitutional law, although it is growing comparatively.⁶⁵⁾ These institutions have autonomy in functional and budgetary matters, they are not integrated into any of the powers of the State, they rest on a counter-majority principle because they are dedicated to technical functions, and they can be interpreted as true mechanisms of political and constitutional balance. Furthermore, his final acts are unchallenged. The SCJN itself has recognized several of these characteristics in jurisprudence theses 12/2008 and 20/2007.

In the case of Mexico, its authoritarian past and high concentration of power must not be forgotten, so from a practical point of view, its origin clearly had a democratizing objective as well as the pluralization of State institutions. If the transition was carried out from within the political system itself, it tried to adapt to a more liberal and pluralistic organic configuration. Furthermore, it should not be forgotten that, given the federal nature of the Mexican Republic, the states themselves

⁶³⁾ Duverger, Maurice, “Influencia de los sistemas electorales en la vida política”, en Albert Batlle i Rubio (coord.), *Diez textos básicos de ciencia política*, 1992.

⁶⁴⁾ Loewenstein, Karl, *Teoría de la Constitución*, Barcelona: Ariel, 1979.

⁶⁵⁾ For example, Colombia, since article 113 of the Constitution recognizes autonomous and independent bodies.

have tended to create some sub-national OCAS, especially in the area of human rights and access to information. In other words, this model of deconcentrating of political power has been carried out at the state level, although with less development, following the same logic of limiting presidential power, in this case, the governors. Similarly, it should be noted that this kind of autonomous institutions, being created by the permanent constituent,⁶⁶⁾ they acquire special protection before the powers of the State, by not submitting to any of them, as well as a singular legal effectiveness.

Following the look of the effects of the autonomous constitutional bodies in the political system, it is necessary to highlight not only the weakening of the presidential figure and therefore of the executive, but also that independent institutions have been created in matters so important for the public administration. Current issues such as monetary policy, the protection of human rights or access to public information and documents. That is, if the effects of the OCAS on the powers of the State must be interpreted, it is in their relationship to the presidency where it is best shown who sought to limit and who has had to give up prerogatives and political power.

For all these reasons, it must be affirmed that the OCAS are an example of constitutional innovation in search of a more limited, more technical and more decentralized political power. Thus, it can be said that the inclusion of this type of organization does not disrupt or injure the traditional division and separation of the powers of the State, but, on the contrary, it deepens the objectives of this doctrine. Indeed, given recent Mexican history, where the entire political system revolved around authoritarian hyper-presidentialism, the subtraction of powers and functions of the executive from new autonomous institutions with constitutional rank must be considered an effective tool to maintain the balance in the system. Especially if we are talking about institutions that cannot have partisan-affiliated officials.

However, it should be noted that the concept of an autonomous constitutional body is neither clear nor well defined. Given that they are, up to now, new independent institutions, with very different technical fields, without similar powers and created at

⁶⁶⁾ Following the name of Diego Valadés in his research Valadés, Diego, "Las funciones de la reforma constitucional", en Valadés, Diego y Carbonell, Miguel (coords.), *El proceso constituyente mexicano. A 150 años de la Constitución de 1857 y 90 de la Constitución de 1917*, p. 819, 2007.

different times, it is difficult to easily establish what an autonomous constitutional body is beyond its constitutional recognition, its location outside of the powers of the State and its controlling and technical role.

So, are they a fourth estate? Given the heterogeneity of the autonomous constitutional bodies, their independence from each other, the non-existence of stony clauses that prevent their reform or even constitutional repeal or their technical nature, we should affirm that they are not exactly a fourth power. They do have the capacity to limit the political power, especially to the executive, and they have served to democratize the State, in the case of genuinely credible and competitive elections, but they do not yet have the constitutional and doctrinal defense of the powers of the State, since they can be subject to a constitutional reform with qualified majorities. We must understand, then, that they are a new way of recognizing institutions with constitutional rank, but that neither correspond to agencies belonging to the executive, nor powers of the State, strictly speaking.

Supporting this thesis, the European constitutional courts should not be forgotten, since their status, powers, independence and autonomy make them true fourth powers. See in this regard the original work of García Pelayo about the Spanish Constitutional Court:⁶⁷⁾ recognized in the Carta Magna, independent of the powers of the State (including the judiciary), autonomous, with the capacity to organize internally and, in addition, have a constitutive character, that is, necessary for the proper functioning. Without the constitutional courts, the rule of law and constitutional justice could not be understood as it unfolds on the European continent. To this, García Pelayo adds the political direction of the State, while the constitutional courts do not make decisions based on what is dictated by other institutions, but rather they have the capacity to decide autonomously and to influence the functioning of the state apparatus. These are the main characteristics that lead García Pelayo to determine that constitutional courts are truly autonomous bodies.

However, it is not so easy to determine that these characteristics, typical of constitutional courts in Europe, are comparable or adaptable to those enjoyed by autonomous constitutional bodies in Mexico. As previously we mentioned, the CNDH

⁶⁷⁾ García Pelayo, Manuel, “El ‘status’ del Tribunal Constitucional”, *op. cit.*, pp. 11-34.

does not have the capacity to impose its decisions, since its recommendations are not binding on the courts. Likewise, the INE, even though it has greater decision-making capacity and the imposition of its resolutions, can be ultimately reviewed by the TEPJF. The same situations could be extended to the remaining autonomous constitutional bodies, which is why their range and political direction of the State are severely limited.

Finally, the characterization and position of the autonomous constitutional bodies in Mexico, as well as the executive, legislative and judiciary powers lead us to rethink and deepen the classic triad of the separation and division of powers. That is, regardless of the rank that we can consider the OCAS to have, it is clear that their specialized, technical, autonomous and separate role from the executive branch is a sign of modernization and adaptation of public administration to the needs that societies demand in the century. XXI. Executives, like parliaments in the past, are sometimes overwhelmed by the increasing complexity required for decision-making in the public sphere, as well as the demand for profiles who are knowledgeable about the *res publica*. The implementation of these new constitutional figures can help executives not make decisions in areas where ideology and popular representation are not preferential to specialized knowledge of the matter. That is, less politics and more science.

6. Conclusions

From the revolutionary era of the eighteenth century until today, there have been numerous developments in the liberal state. Constitutions have recognized new fundamental rights, the role of the state in the economy and the society changed and the institutional organization of public administration was transformed. In general terms, the public power became more complex, technical, professional and acquired a greater capacity to influence the day-to-day. This evolution has often been analyzed from the evolution of fundamental rights or from the new configuration of the forms of government. Also, is usually the list of fundamental rights recognized in the

Constitution a good tool to know the capacity of liberal states to adapt to the political and cultural changes in current societies.

In the same way, the constitutional amendments that have been made in the recent decades brought a new relation between the powers of the state. In the parliamentary regimes, the legislative branch tended to lose its capacity to influence the stability of the executive. It is usually named as the rationalization of parliamentarism, and it is relatively common in the European parliamentary systems. In presidentialism, the constitutions tended to limit the dominance of the president. Example of that, the Latin Americans constitutions introduced several modifications like a prime minister (Perú), non-continuous reelection (Uruguay, Perú) or the organization of electoral processes independent of the executive branch, like Mexico.

These changes and reconfigurations of the state have been both continuous and progressive in these 250 years of constitutional life. However, we must highlight one last impulse and organic innovation: the creation of the Autonomous Constitutional Bodies in Mexico as a good example of this. It was a huge advance to achieve a deconcentration of political power and, specially, to weaken the authoritarian Mexican presidentialism.

Indeed, the constitutional recognition of these institutions and their autonomy, independence and faculties represent a new twist to the doctrine of separation of powers and division of the state. We must not place them in any of the three classic powers, but we cannot bring them together in a new and hypothetical fourth power of the state. They are very different from each other, where objectives, means and themes are not comparable. To this, it has to be added that they are not involved in the direction of the state genuinely speaking and its possible disappearance should not disrupt the liberal nature of the state as if power were. Consequently, they do not have the autonomy and capacity to resist constitutional reforms of the European constitutional courts.

Therefore, they have a *sui generis* political and legal nature, standing in a differentiated way over the various government agencies that belong to the executive power, but they do not have the organic category of the constitutional courts of Europe as we mentioned. However, the important role that the OCAS have played and

do play in the democratization of Mexico since the 1990s should be highlighted. They served to limit the authoritarian hyper-presidentialism of the PRI, which plunged the republic into decades of arbitrariness, despotism and lack of political pluralism. Previously of the creation of OCAS, the executive organized fraudulent electoral processes (real basis of the dictatorship of the single party of the Mexican twentieth century). The research of human rights violations was also a task of the government, and the judiciary power was hardly independent of the Head of state. Now, however, the CNDH is a constitutional and independent agency that protects and research any violations of human right and it has a direct way to the Interamerican system of human rights.

Likewise, other benefits for democracy that have been derived from the constitutional recognition of the INAI, the INEGI, BANXICO or the IFT, among others, could be enumerated: transparency, public decisions with a technical and non-partisan basis and the consolidation of a liberal and non-partisan economic model and non-personal basis.

The CNDH is an example of this, since through its legal nature as OCA it has played a fundamental role in the non-judicial way for the protection of human rights. The powers that it has been acquiring, such as the investigation of serious violations and its duty to adopt inter-American jurisprudence, have been added to those already existing in order to make its work more effective. In other words, it has been configured as a control to the Mexican political power in its three levels of government (federal, state and municipal) and is also a link between the inter-American human rights system and the Mexican public administration. It therefore supposes a new aspect of action of the autonomous constitutional bodies: the international plane and its integration into the national order.

Finally, it remains to highlight the importance and rise of this type of institutions without a democratic-electoral basis. It involves risks in their configuration and design, such as their insufficient constitutional protection; and they represent a new evolution of the Liberal State created approximately 250 years ago. The constitutional model is constantly evolving and the creation of new agencies and OCAS is a new stage that highlights the consolidation of political pluralism, a technical decision-making and the

weakening of the executive power, real concern for the experts on Latin American presidentialism. It must not be forgotten that full democracy is a certainly unattainable ideal, which gradually changes based on the mentality and demands of the societies, so the evolution of the liberal state is natural and desirable.

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<http://dx.doi.org/10.24324/KIACL.2021.27.1.205>